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explore the
development of
LNG emergency
and incident
response
guidelines in
Europe.

HOT TOPIC

Safety in the LNG industry is a hot topic, particularly now that LNG is increasingly becoming a fuel of the future. While it is a challenge, insights are being developed by various groups. However, the information is not readily available to third parties. A number of European ports recently worked together to map existing knowledge on emergency and incident responses and develop new guidelines regarding LNG incident response along the Rhine Corridor. The results of this LNG emergency and incident response study have been collated and published to benefit other ports.¹ The final report is a big step forward in LNG safety in Europe.

Some of the recommendations that have resulted from the report include the following:

- ▶ Make an inventory of LNG hotspots per region, based on the necessary contours.
- ▶ Prepare detailed local emergency plans, taking into account the local infrastructure.
- ▶ Share skills and knowledge with public and private parties.

- Come prepared with appropriate portable gas detection equipment and sufficient water supply.

The document is a source of information about the current safety techniques available to minimise the impact of LNG incidents. It informs emergency response organisations how to prepare themselves to manage credible LNG incidents on inland navigation along the Rhine-Main-Danube corridor. The report describes four such incidents in more detail. Emergency response plans for these incidents – with specific emergency response strategy – are also included.

Figure 1. Modelling of LNG vapour cloud contours (UEL and LEL) after collision with bridge (detailed scenario 1).

Figure 2. Firefighting strategy summary.

LNG evaporation rates (LNG pool on water)	Density	Evaporation rate	Regression rate
LNG	430 – 470 kg/m ³	0.16 kg/m ² /sec. 15 m ³ /m ² /min.	20 mm/min.

LNG Masterplan

The study is co-financed by the EU's TEN-T Programme and is part of the 'LNG Masterplan for Rhine-Main-Danube' project.

The LNG Masterplan aims to create a platform for the cooperation of authorities and industry stakeholders with the purpose of facilitating the creation of a harmonised European regulatory framework for LNG as a fuel and cargo in inland navigation, and promoting the introduction of LNG as a fuel and cargo for inland shipping.

LNG is considered to be an important opportunity for the inland waterway transport sector, however it is not a remedy for every structural and economic problem. All efforts of the LNG Masterplan are based on a realistic and integrated European approach. One of the visions of the plan is that the inland ports on the Rhine-Main-Danube axis will become key distribution centres for LNG. Inland terminals will function as satellites to the interior, enabling LNG to reach other pioneer markets, such as the public (transport) sector and the heavy duty transport industry (buses, waste collection trucks, city logistics), as well as the energy industry.

A study to increase awareness

The aim of the study was to explore and gather existing knowledge regarding the transportation of LNG and the use of LNG-powered vessels on the waterways, as well as to determine possible LNG leak scenarios that an incident response team could face. The target group is emergency response organisations in the inland waterway transport sector, such as the fire brigade, police, ambulance and harbour/river authorities. The information gained as a result of the study helps these organisations to deal with situations that have escalated outside the capability of initial responders, such as the ship's crew and operators. The report is used to increase awareness in handling such incidents, make recommendations concerning the resources required for a response, and provide guidelines for the training required for incident response.

Executing the study

A consortium between Falck Risc and the Rotterdam Unified Fire Department was chosen in mid-2014 to execute the study, due to their specific knowledge of LNG technology and incident preparedness in inland navigation. The assignment was set by the Rhine Port Group, which consists of the Port of Rotterdam Authority, the Port of Antwerp, the Port of Mannheim, the Port of Strasbourg and the Port of Switzerland.

Falck Risc provides safety training and consultancy for both high risk and low risk industrial companies. Each year, over 12 000 members of industrial or public fire brigades are trained by Falck Risc at training centres in the Netherlands. The company also has an emergency response team, which assists with incidents onboard ships.

From study to report

The report document consists of two main parts. The first part presents an overview of existing knowledge of LNG incident response, training and education along the Rhine corridor, including:

- ▶ Overview of existing knowledge and existing guidelines for incident response in small scale LNG along the Rhine corridor for inland navigation.
- ▶ Overview of existing emission and escalation scenarios for LNG as a fuel and LNG as a cargo in small scale LNG along the Rhine corridor for inland navigation.
- ▶ Emergency and incident response scenarios in small scale LNG along the Rhine corridor for inland navigation. Scenarios include all incidents that could occur with an LNG-fuelled vessel and a vessel that has LNG as cargo.
- ▶ Incidents and emergencies are presented in a matrix, displaying the types of LNG-fuelled vessels and vessels sailing with LNG as cargo.

Figure 3. Frosted detail of an LNG-truck. Source: Port of Rotterdam Authority/Falck Risc.

Figure 4. Controlled emergency training at the LNG-specialised Falck Risc location.

Table 2. Required training elements selected for each type of response class

Level	Response class	Knowledge elements	Understanding elements	Skill requirements	Estimated training duration
Incipient stage response	Terminal operators	1, 2, 9	2, 9	9	1 day
	Tank truck drivers	1, 2, 9	2, 9	9	
	Ship's crew	1, 2, 9	2, 9	9	
Advanced response	Operational firefighters	1 – 9	1 – 9	1 – 9	2 days
	Operational harbour and inland waterway response personnel	1 – 9	1 – 9	3, 5, 6, 9	1 day
	Medical services	1	2		0.5 day
	Tactical command functions	1 – 10	1 – 10	10	2 days
	Strategic command functions	1 – 10	1 – 10	10	2 days

Key:

1 = properties and behaviour of LNG; 2 = descriptions and hazards of LNG; 3 = LNG inland vessels, design and safety engineering; 4 = the LNG handling and processes; 5 = processes that may lead to a flammable vapour cloud; 6 = control of a vapour cloud; 7 = controlling fire and firefighting; 8 = measuring a gas cloud – temperature; 9 = firefighting strategies; 10 = incident management LNG

- ▶ Identification of gaps in the response equipment necessary for emergency response in small scale LNG along the Rhine corridor for inland navigation.

The second part of the document consists of the following:

- ▶ Incident preparedness guidelines for small scale LNG in inland navigation.
- ▶ Guidelines for education and training on incident response applied to small scale LNG in inland navigation. Where training is necessary, these guidelines describe the required training elements for each target group.

Conclusion

The study has shown that much knowledge and experience is already available within the EU concerning high levels of safety when transporting dangerous goods on inland waterways. It has also shown that local emergency services and port authorities are professional organisations working hard to prevent any kind of incident with dangerous goods on European waterways.

Nevertheless, the recent introduction of the international carriage of LNG on European inland waterways has introduced a new phenomenon for emergency services and port authorities. It should be remembered that LNG is a cryogenic gas, stored in its liquid phase at a temperature of -162°C , reducing the volume by about 600 times compared to the size of its original gas volume. The evaporation rate of released LNG on water is high: approximately $15\text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2/\text{min}$. Released LNG behaves as a gas that is heavier than air, bringing with it the risk of asphyxiation.

Due to its nature, it requires specific handling procedures as well as a different approach to emergency and incident response.

LNG in Rotterdam

Within the TEN-T context, the Port of Rotterdam leads the Masterplan programme that promotes the use of inland shipping for LNG. Why is LNG so important for Rotterdam? And what is the current status of LNG developments?

The Gate terminal is located in Rotterdam, and is the first import LNG terminal in the Netherlands, with Gasunie and Vopak as the main shareholders. Both Gate terminal and the Port of Rotterdam have extended the business model to supplement the import function of the terminal, with new functions such as LNG trading and back loading, and the use of LNG as a fuel for shipping and trucking. In this respect, Gate terminal and the Port of Rotterdam have started to build LNG break bulk facilities. This project will further strengthen the port's ambition to become a leading European import, export and bunkering hub for LNG.

In 2013, Rotterdam created rules, regulations and port bylaws as the first port in the world to allow for ship-to-ship bunkering of LNG. This set a precedent for other ports to follow and contributed to the creation of a global standard. Bunkering is available in the harbour, and two trucking gas stations have opened at strategic locations near a busy truck route, which runs through the Netherlands to Belgium, France, and the Ruhr Area of Germany. The Port of Rotterdam not only cooperates with other European ports through the Masterplan project, but has also started to cooperate with other ports throughout the world, including Los Angeles in the US and Singapore, to ensure a unilateral standard. **LNG**

Reference

1. 'LNG Masterplan for Rhine-Maine-Danube – D 2.4.4 Emergency and incident response study', April 2015, http://www.lngmasterplan.eu/images/gallery/Deliverables/D_244_Emergency_and_incident_response_study_v1.0_FINAL_2015-4-15.pdf